

Modern english teaching technologies

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini samarali o‘rganishning bir necha yo‘llari va til o‘rganishdagi ba‘zi zamonaviy ta‘lim texnologiyalari keltirilgan. Shuningdek, til o‘rganish jarayonida til o‘rganuvchilarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratish ta‘kidlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: til, zamonaviy mustaqil til o‘rganish, ta‘lim texnologiyalari, loyiha, qiziqish, faoliyat, interaktiv usullar.

Annotation. In this article, it is given several ways to learn English effectively and some of the modern learning technologies in language learning as well. It is also emphasized to pay special attention to the development of creative abilities of language learners in the process of language learning.

Keywords: language, modern independent language learning, educational technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods.

Абстрактный. В данной статье представлены несколько способов эффективного изучения английского языка и некоторые современные образовательные технологии в изучении языка. Также подчеркнуто уделять особое внимание развитию творческих способностей изучающих язык в процессе изучения языка.

Ключевые слова: язык, современное самостоятельное изучение языка, образовательные технологии, проект, интерес, активность, интерактивные методы.

Nowadays the main focus is on the student, his personality and unique interior focused on the world. Therefore, the main goal of the modern teacher It is the choice of methods and forms of organization of educational activities that optimally correspond to the set goal of personal development of students. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools is increasing rising. It is not

only new technical tools, but also new forms of teaching and methods, a new approach to the learning process. Basics of teaching foreign languages the goal is to form the communicative culture of schoolchildren and to develop to teach the practical mastery of a foreign language. Teaching and learning English in the research process is popular methods, internet sources were used. During the writing of the article, the principles of theoretical, deductive, conclusion, analysis and synthesis, logicity were used.

The task of the teacher is for the practical acquisition of the language for each student to create conditions for every student to demonstrate his activity and creativity is to choose such teaching methods that allow. The task of the teacher is different is to activate the student's cognitive activity in the process of teaching languages. In partnership learning, project methodology, use of new information technologies, modern pedagogical technologies such as Internet resources to the individual in the educational process helps to implement a focused approach, children abilities, of teaching taking into account their level of learning provides individualization and differentiation. Computer in foreign language classes forms of working with training programs include: learning vocabulary, practice pronunciation, teaching dialogic and monologic speech, to write to teach, development of grammatical events.

The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. Global Internet essential for students and teachers located anywhere in the world provides conditions for obtaining any information that is: regional geographic materials, news in youth life, articles from newspapers and magazines and others. This is one technology that enables student-centered learning is a project method as a method of development of creativity, knowledge activity and independence.

The typology of projects is diverse. Projects are monoprosjects, collective, oral can be divided into speech, concrete, written and Internet projects. In actual, practice often research projects, creative, practice-oriented and informative you have to deal with mixed projects where characters are present. Project work language a multi-faceted approach to learning that includes reading, listening, speaking and grammar covers. Project method to develop active independent thinking of students helps and directs them to joint research work. In my opinion, project-based teaching teaches children to cooperate and learning moral values such as mutual aid and the ability to empathize educates, forms creativity and activates students. In general, in the project teaching process, teaching and education are inseparable.

The project method improves students' communication skills, communication culture, the ability to form thoughts concisely and easily, tolerance to the opinions of communication partners develops the ability to receive information from various sources, processes it using modern computer technologies, a natural need arises creates a language environment that contributes to being. The project form of the work gives students the accumulated knowledge on the subject is one of the most relevant technologies that allow to use. Students expand their horizons, the limits of language knowledge, more practical gather experience of using, listening and hearing speech in a foreign language learn, understand each other when protecting projects. Children reference books, dictionaries, work with a computer and thus a real language create an opportunity to directly communicate with, which is only a textbook in the classroom does not provide language learning.

Working on a project is a creative process. Student independently or teacher seeks a solution to the problem under his guidance, for this not only knowing the language, but having a large amount of subject knowledge, creative, communicative and intellectual skills are required.

The project method in the course of foreign languages is a program on almost any subject can be used within the materials. Working on projects involves imagination, fantasy, develops creative thinking, independence and other personal qualities.

Introduction of information technologies to education, information perception and re greatly diversifies the work process. Computer, Internet and multimedia due to the large volume with further analysis and sorting to the students a unique opportunity for data acquisition was created. Educational activities, motivational bases are also expanding significantly. From multimedia in the conditions of use, students get information from newspapers, television, themselves conduct interviews and hold teleconferences.

The basis for assessing the level of knowledge of a foreign language in the language portfolio technology criteria is the test. The priority of this technology is to direct the educational process from the teacher to the student. The reader, in turn his is consciously responsible for the results of educational activities. The above technology leads to the gradual formation of students' skills of independent assimilation of information. In general, the language portfolio is multifunctional and contributes to the development of multilingualism.

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